

The Correlation Between Climate Change-Induced Excessive Heat Exposure and Mental Health Outcomes in Adolescents Residing in Low-and Middle-Income Countries: A Scoping Review

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Abstract

Introduction: Climate change is putting humanity at great risk. Increasing frequency of heatwaves, droughts, hurricanes, cyclones and heavy precipitation caused by climate change are having catastrophic effects on the ecological system, agriculture and human health. Extreme heat, stemming from climate change, has both direct and indirect implications on the mental well-being of adolescents. This scoping review examines how extreme heat affects the mental health of adolescents, especially those living in underprivileged communities in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs).

Methods: Out of 99,565 screened articles, twenty studies were retained for an extensive analysis in the scoping review. These studies included both peer-reviewed and grey literature with pre-defined criteria focusing on the effects of climate-related disaster exposure and how such exposures impact mental health outcomes. The scarcity of literature from LMICs led to the expansion of the scope in this study to include studies older than 10 years and conducted in high-income countries (HICs).

Results: A review of 20 studies in this scoping review highlighted the association between extreme heat and its cascading effects with higher rates of depression, post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), sleep disturbances, suicidal ideation, aggression, intimate partner violence and academic underperformance in adolescents.

Conclusions: Excessive heat increases the risk of developing mental health illnesses thus intensifying poverty, migration, exposure to trauma and unfavorable learning environments. Effective adaptation measures heavily hinge on policymakers viewing excessive heat in tandem with climate-related events and other priority development issues for a country. Intervention and adaptation strategies should be integrated and harmonized synchronously with youth, communities,

mental health and healthcare professional training programs, migration organization programs, initiatives, and capacity-building activities.

Keywords: Academic Performance; Adolescents; Climate Change; Displacement; Extreme Heat; Mental Health; Post-traumatic Stress Disorder.

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INTRODUCTION

The unprecedented pace of climate change (CC) has caused serious concerns, particularly among youth. Observable outcomes, such as heatwaves, rising sea levels and extreme weather threaten human health, economies, politics, ecosystems, and social cohesions, and disproportionately affect disadvantaged communities.

NASA defines CC as “prolonged changes in average weather patterns with synonymous impact at local and global scales” [1]. These transformations originated during the Industrial Revolution and continue due to increasing consumer demand, excessive deforestation, agriculture, and fossil fuel combustion. This, in turn, results in elevated levels of heat-trapping greenhouse gases in the Earth’s atmosphere, creating a “canopy” that raises temperatures and drives geophysical changes. These changes encompass rising sea levels, heightened carbon dioxide (CO₂) and methane levels, and an escalation in the frequency and intensity of extreme weather events [2].

Climate change profoundly impacts human health through multiple channels, leading to death and a myriad of illnesses. Climate change has created a humanitarian crisis, with projections of 250,000 annual deaths from undernutrition, malaria, diarrhea and heat stress between 2030 and 2050 [3]. WHO defines a heatwave as a period where local excess heat accumulates over a sequence of unusually hot days and nights. Heatwaves have been linked to 489,000 deaths annually between 2000-2019 [4]. The period from July 21st-23rd, 2024 was recorded to be the hottest in recorded history [5]. As heatwaves increase in frequency, duration and intensity, global adaptability measures are vital.

The ecological system humans depend on for survival has been stressed by CC. The World Economic Forum (2024) [6] reported 40 million people in Africa, 17% of Europe and 40% of southern United States are facing drought due to heatwaves. Currently, global temperatures are 1.1°C above pre-industrial levels. Consequently, heat-induced droughts, the second-highest weather-related cause of mortality, are projected to result in 3.2 million deaths by 2050 and result in \$12.5 trillion in economic losses due to reduced productivity. These climate impacts will exacerbate global health disparities.

Climate change is having a profound and cascading impact on humanity, with effects manifesting immediately and lasting years after the initial event. High temperatures and intensified rainfall contribute to the onset of malaria epidemics, dengue fever, antibiotic-resistant infections, increase mortality, poverty and displacement [7]. These repercussions stemming from Earth’s geophysical changes extend beyond physical health to impact mental health (depression, post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), anxiety and addiction) with the magnitude varying based on individual, social, and physical vulnerabilities. It was stated in the World Economic Forum (2024) [6] that high temperatures can lead to six climate

events: floods, droughts, heatwaves, tropical storms, wildfires and sea level rising, all of which share mental health conditions as a common health outcome (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Cause-effect relationship of climate events [6].

Developing nations are suffering the most from CC, despite contributing very little to the causes of global warming. Low- and Middle-Income Countries (LMICs), where agriculture employs a significant portion of the population (59% in LICs and 38% in MICs) are particularly vulnerable to CC, which exacerbates food insecurity [8]. Climate events such as flooding, land degradation, and drought have resulted in malnutrition, increased vector-borne diseases, and displacement. Studies, including those reviewed in this scoping review, clearly demonstrate a strong correlation between social determinants of health (SDH) and health outcomes associated with CC.

Inadequate nutrition can impair cognitive development and lead to mental health disorders [9]. Higher temperatures and increased CO₂ levels promote faster plant growth, reducing nutrition absorption crucial for brain health. Zinc and iron deficiency are linked to neurogenesis, potentially leading to depression, psychosis and psychiatric disorders [10, 11]. Air pollution from heat-related wildfires can cause inflammatory cell damage if they reach the brain via blood vessels, leading to increased risk of autism, attention-deficit or hyperactivity disorder, reduced cognitive ability, depression, suicide, and behavioural problems in children [9].

A systematic review by Xu et al. [12] found that heatwaves significantly increase hospital admissions among children for renal and respiratory issues. This rise in morbidity among school-age children cascades into missed school days and subsequently impaired cognitive and intellectual performance. Heatwaves alone should not be considered as the sole cause of increased illnesses and deaths, but rather as triggers to temperature-sensitive diseases and conditions.

The warming of the Earth's atmosphere contributes to rising sea levels, more frequent cyclones, flooding caused by glacier melts and other extreme weather, all intensify displacement and migration [13]. According to the UN High Commissioner for Refugees, an annual average of 21.5 million people are displaced by natural disasters. This figure is conservative, as some countries are not fully tracking migration patterns. The UN predicted 143 million people will be displaced over the next 30 years due to climate-related events [14]. The United Nations Children's Fund reported that between 2016 and 2021, there were 43.1 million internal displacements of children (equivalent to 20,000 children displaced per day) because of climate-related events [15]. As the planet continues to get hotter, the number of 'climate refugees' (people forced to leave their homes due to climate crisis) will reach unmanageable levels. Repetitive episodes of extreme heat in certain regions have resulted in rainfall stress and crop failure; consequently, forcing families into internal or external migration [16]. Exposure to repeated geological disasters could embed posttraumatic disorders, which could lead to chronic psychological disorders (depression, anxiety, etc.) if left untreated or unchecked in the early stages [17].

The relocation of children and adolescents to an unfamiliar environment, detaching them from their communal support system (parents, relatives, neighbors, teachers and/or friends), and disrupting their daily routines (i.e., schooling), further impacts their vulnerable physiological and psychological well-being. Displaced populations face limited resources and healthcare access heightening the rates of sexually transmitted diseases, unwanted pregnancies, sexual exploitation during climate-induced extreme heat and weather events [17].

In research, adolescents are grouped with children (0-14 years) or adults (15-60 years old), or alternatively, may be grouped into a singular category alongside all children aged 0-18 years, failing to address their unique physical and mental stressors. This oversight creates a critical gap in literature and policymaking. Despite the sparsity of literature comparing the effects of stress on the adolescent and adult brain, those available such as the work of Romeo (2013) highlight the immature stress-sensitive limbic and cortical brain areas in adolescents are more susceptible to stressors compared to those of adults, with structural and functional changes persisting long after stress events. Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) reveals delayed brain development in the prefrontal cortex and amygdala (emotional regulation) until the mid-20s [18]. The cumulative traumatic exposure in adolescents, especially those with pre-existing mental illnesses, can worsen their mental state. The lack of age-specific data results in the misunderstanding of the needs of this demographic group and underrepresentation of adolescent needs in global public health and policy.

The purpose of this scoping review is to examine the impact of climate-related extreme heat on adolescents in LICs and MICs. It also intends to bring attention to policymakers and health officials about the unique challenges faced by adolescents in vulnerable communities. Climate change poses critical environmental, developmental and public health challenges. Understanding what adolescents experience during the climate crisis is vital to addressing their concerns and improving resilience. Predicting and appreciating the effects of CC on the overall health system requires an understanding of the exposure-response function of the entire human body. Adolescent resilience can only be improved by devising inclusive, flexible, and productive mitigation and adaptation strategies through this understanding.

METHODS

Search strategy and study selection

WHO's definition of health as "a state of complete physical, mental and social well-being and not merely the absence of disease or infirmity" [19] and SDH as "the non-medical factors that influence health outcomes" [20] were the guiding frameworks in the search and analysis stages of this scoping review. A systematic literature search was performed using PubMed, and supported by databases like Google Scholar, Elsevier, ResearchGate and Science Direct to gain full-text articles. Relevant websites such as WHO, United Nations Environmental Program, Google, government sites and others were also utilized to obtain supporting articles and grey literature. Keywords such as: *climate change, climate*

crisis, extreme heat, heatwaves, adolescents, children, mental health, migration, forced displacement, academic performance, learning, school performance, classroom temperature, refugees, natural disasters, and mitigation and adaptation were combined using Boolean operators “AND”, “OR” and truncations (*) to retrieve and refine results. The search yielded 20 articles (Table A1). Table 1 demonstrates the employed search approach.

Table 1. Search strategy used in journal retrieval.

SEARCH: Academics	<p>Keywords: educational performance, performance in school, test (s), learning, classroom temperature, academics, exam(s), examination(s) AND children, adolescents, kids “Educational performance”[tw] OR “school performance”[tw] OR test*[tw] OR learning[tw] OR “classroom temperature”[tw] OR academics[tw] OR exam*[tw] OR examination(s)[tw] AND children[tw] OR adolescents[tw] OR kids[tw] MeSH Terms: "Academic Performance"[Mesh]</p>
SEARCH 2: Migration	<p>Keywords: migration, forced displacement, AND children, adolescents, kids, low-income country, middle-income country, LMICs Migration[tw] OR “forced displacement”[tw] AND children[tw] OR adolescents[tw] OR kids[tw] OR “low-income country”*[tw] OR “middle-income country”*[tw] OR LMIC*[tw] MeSH Terms: "Human Migration"[Mesh] AND "Emigration and Immigration"[Mesh]</p>
SEARCH 3: Climate Change	<p>Keywords: climate change, extreme heat, natural disasters, heatwaves, climate crisis, low-income countries, middle-income countries, LMICs “Climate Change”[tw] OR “extreme heat”[tw] OR “natural disasters”[tw] OR “natural disaster”*[tw] OR heatwave*[tw] OR “climate crisis”[tw] OR “low-income country”*[tw] OR “middle-income country”*[tw] OR LMIC*[tw] MeSH Terms: "Climate Change"[Mesh]</p>
SEARCH 4	<p>"Academic Performance"[Mesh] OR “educational performance”[tw] OR “school performance”[tw] OR test*[tw] OR learning[tw] OR “classroom temperature”[tw] OR academics[tw] OR exam*[tw] OR examination(s)[tw] AND children[tw] OR adolescents[tw] OR kids[tw] AND "Human Migration"[Mesh] AND "Emigration and Immigration"[Mesh] OR Migration[tw] OR “forced displacement”[tw] AND children[tw] OR adolescents[tw] OR kids[tw] OR “low-income country”*[tw] OR “middle-income country”*[tw] OR LMIC*[tw] AND "Climate Change"[Mesh] OR “Climate Change”[tw] OR “extreme heat”[tw] OR “natural disasters”[tw] OR “natural disaster”*[tw] OR heatwave*[tw] OR “climate crisis”[tw] OR “low-income country”*[tw] OR “middle-income country”*[tw] OR LMIC*[tw]</p>

A preliminary search yielded 99,565 articles. To limit results, the search was restricted to human subjects and full-text English articles from 2005-2024. An additional 26 articles were sourced through reference lists and Google. Eighteen articles were eliminated due to duplication. A preliminary screening process, which involved reviewing titles,

abstracts and methodology excluded an additional 98,933 articles based on the criteria in Figure 2. A full-text review rendered 616 articles unsuitable as they did not address the research topic (i.e., immigrant generation mental health studies). No restrictions were applied regarding study location, publication country and subject gender.

Figure 2. PRISMA diagram showing the study inclusion and exclusion criteria.

Data extraction and thematic analysis

The scoping review examined the available empirical data on the multitude of adverse effects of extreme heat on adolescents' well-being and identify the gap in the literature to shape future research. Systematic analysis was conducted to discern and extract recurring mental health themes associated with both direct and indirect extreme heat exposure. Consolidated data were categorized into themes specifically addressing mental health amid direct and indirect thermal stress: (i) academic and cognitive function, (ii) psychological and emotional distress, and (iii) social and behavioral function. The data was charted to include the year of publication, study design, the geographical area of study, participant information, aim/objective of the study and summary of findings (Table A1). A comprehensive review

of the collected data yielded five studies addressing academic and cognitive themes, ten studies focusing on psychological and emotional distress, and seven studies examining social and behavioral disruption in adolescents. Some studies had overlapping themes but were categorized based on their primary focus. Comparative analysis identified commonalities and discrepancies amongst the studies. Recurring patterns were consolidated into datasets for a smoother interpretation of their underlying significance. The findings highlight the synergy between CC, extreme heat, and mental health in adolescents emphasizing the need for more research to address these complex interactions.

RESULTS

The scoping review revealed that most evidence-based research is predominately from high- and upper-middle-income countries, like the United States of America (USA) and China, with limited studies from vulnerable regions, such as Africa and South America, which face the greatest impacts of CC [21]. This underscores disparities in research funding and representation. To enhance preparedness measures in vulnerable regions, it is crucial to have data representation from such areas. Funding organizations and governments should prioritize the inclusion of knowledge and expertise from authors in LMICs in literature.

This scoping review acknowledges several limitations. First, literature search was restricted to English-language journals, which created a language bias. Additionally, the retrieval of peer-reviewed journals from sources such as PubMed and Elsevier resulted in over-representation of studies from high- and middle-income countries. The rarity of adverse climate events compared to common health events such as influenza necessitated the inclusion of literature older than 10 years. Lastly, the interconnected nature of climate event, such as extreme heat contributing to flooding or hurricanes, made it challenging to study exclusively extreme heat without considering the compounding effects of related events (flooding or hurricanes).

Twenty studies met the inclusion criteria (Figure 2) and were classified into three thematic categories: academic and cognitive function (5 studies), psychological and emotional distress (10 studies), and social and behavioral function (5 studies).

Academic and cognitive function

Classroom environments, unlike workplace and residential dwellings, necessitate unique policies conducive for optimal learning outcomes. Qualitative studies by Dapi et al. [22] in Cameroon and Bidassey-Manilal et al. [23] in South Africa found that high classroom temperatures negatively impacted children's health and performance, causing headaches (OR = 1.02), fatigue (OR = 0.97), feeling very hot (OR = 1.17), low concentration, dizziness (OR = 1.18), reduced writing speed (OR = 0.93), and sleepiness (OR = 1.12). Dapi et al. [22] identified a gender difference in heat perception, with girls being more vulnerable to heat [22, 23]. These findings highlighted the need for larger studies to further explore gender differences in thermal comfort among the sexes and address gender bias in classrooms and workplaces.

Quantitative studies by Haverinen-Shughnessy et al. [24] and Goodman et al. [25] provide corroborating evidence on the detrimental effects of high classroom temperatures on adolescent academic performance. Haverinen-Shughnessy et al. [24] found that lower temperatures improved 5th-graders' mathematics scores, with variations in temperature preferences across ethnicity and socioeconomic status. Caucasian and Asian students preferred lower temperatures, while Native American, African American and Hispanic students preferred higher temperatures. Additionally, students eligible for free lunch programs preferred higher temperatures than those who were not [24]. A study by Goodman et al. [25] involving 10 million PSAT-retakers in the USA found a negative correlation between hotter school years and learning outcomes, with a disproportionate effect on minority students [25].

Gibbs et al. [26] conducted a four-year cohort study on 24,642 Australian adolescents uncovering decline on academic achievements in reading and numeracy among students in post-disaster communities, particularly in high-

impact areas. No significant trend was observed in writing, spelling and grammar scores. No gender differences were observed in any of the scores. These findings demonstrate the long-term impact of disaster exposure on academic performance and the need for targeted resilience measures.

Psychological and emotional distress

There is ample research linking extreme heat-induced by CC to psychological and emotional distress, including internalizing behaviors, such as loneliness, guilt, irritability, sadness, fearfulness, and social withdrawal. Sugg et al. (2019) assessed 59,000 crisis-text-line (CTL) conversations, with 80% involving individuals under 22 years of age. Sugg and his colleagues uncovered a substantial increase in support-seeking behavior (related to anxiety, depression, suicide ideation, self-harm and relationship issues) during high temperatures in urban areas. For instance, Atlanta risk ratio (RR) rose from 1.01 at 15°C (Confidence Interval (CI): 1.00-1.02) to RR 1.70 at 37°C (CI: 1.07-2.70). Chicago's RR rose from 1.12 at 12°C (CI: 1.00-1.23) to RR: 1.64 at 35°C (CI: 1.26-2.15) and New York City's RR rose from 1.14 at 19°C (CI: 1.03-1.31) to RR: 2.04 at 38°C (CI: 1.73-3.29). A pronounced increase in CTL was observed in northern cities with seasonal temperature shifts, while no significant association was observed in southern cities with stable climates. A noticeable decline in CTL in August suggests that school commencement plays a protective role on adolescent mental health. Future research should factor in air pollution, solar radiation and humidity as these variables might affect mental health [27].

Zuromski et al. [27] corroborate the research findings by Sugg et al. [28] and Younan et al. [29] on adolescent behavior following climate-induced events. Zuromski et al.'s study of 2,000 participants revealed that adolescents with prior interpersonal violence (IPV) were more vulnerable to PTSD (6.40%), Major Depressive Disorder (MDD) (7.40%) and suicidal ideation (5.30%) post-climate induced tornado. Participants with IPV were almost 2.5 times more likely to have suicidal ideation (OR = 2.42), with suicidal ideation linked to PTSD (OR = 1.12) and MDD (OR = 1.68).

Three additional studies also uncovered the indirect impact of extreme heat-induced natural events on adolescents' suicidal ideation. Akkaya-Kalayci et al. [30] identified internal migration in Turkey as a risk factor for suicidal behavior. Brown et al. [31] found a negative mental health impact (depression and suicidal thoughts) on adolescents in wildfire-affected communities. Catani et al. [32] established the existence of a dose-effect relationship between cumulative stress exposure (i.e., natural disasters, war, family violence) and PTSD severity, linking PTSD to increase suicidal symptoms and MDD. This corroborates the findings by Zuromski et al. [28]. Dean & Stain [33] also support the positive affiliation between the cumulative effect of natural disasters and the inability of adolescents to cope with stress. A cumulative increase in drought exposure was associated with increased emotional and behavioral difficulties. A longitudinal study would add more value to this research to assess if resilience develops with cumulative drought exposure.

An additional four studies demonstrated adolescents' susceptibility to mental health issues, such as PTSD, as analyzed by Zuromski et al. [28] and Catani et al. [32]. Ahmad et al. [34] observed high PTSD prevalence among flood-affected adolescents in Pakistan, with displaced adolescents and girls being more vulnerable. This study supports the protective role of schools as observed by Sugg et al. [27].

Mental health issues can be experienced both immediately and post-traumatic events. Taukeni et al. [35] found children, particularly older ones, continue to experience PTSD for up to two years after a disastrous flood. Brown et al. [36] linked severe traumatic events with sleep disturbances in youth, ultimately impacting concentration and alertness at school.

Social and behavioral function

Extreme heat and climate-related events have both personal and societal impacts. For instance, a teenager displaced by drought may develop PTSD and aggression, leading to fights and bullying at school, affecting the attendance of other students at the school as observed by Meyer et al. [37].

Research on the impact of CC-induced migration on adolescents' social and behavioral function is scarce. A large qualitative study by Temple et al. [38] investigated the impact of Hurricane Ike (coast of Texas) on substance use and dating violence among youth. The study concluded two points: non-evacuated boys were significantly more likely than not to engage in sexual assault (OR = 3.19) and/or be victims of sexual assault (OR = 3.73) compared to evacuated boys. Secondly, non-evacuated youth showed higher rates of excessive alcohol consumption (OR_{boys} = 1.83, OR_{girls}=2.45), marijuana (OR_{boys} = 2.10, OR_{girls}=2.97) and cocaine (OR_{boys} = 5.41, OR_{girls}=4.73) compared to evacuated youth. The inclusion of collective retrospective data from the participants' core communities (parents, teachers, family members) rather than just subjective participant data would have strengthened the study.

Adolescents' externalized behaviors can be triggered not only by migration and displacement but also directly by extreme heat. A three-year longitudinal study by Younan et al. [29] linked extreme temperature to increased externalizing behaviors in urban adolescents, including both physical (fighting, destroying things, attacking others, etc.) and verbal behaviors (teasing, screaming, arguing, etc.). Hot summers led to aggressive behavior equivalent to 1.5-3.0 years of delay in age-related behavioral maturation. This connection was 2-3 times stronger among girls and 1.5-4 times greater among families of lower socioeconomic status, but significantly lower among participants living in neighborhoods with ample green space. A 1°C rise in ambient temperature increased aggression scores by 0.23-0.41-points. No link was found between temperature variations and delinquent behavior such as lying, stealing, or cheating. The use of subjective parental reports to assess externalizing behavior introduced a potential bias factor as parents may not be fully aware or forthcoming of their children's behavior at and outside the home.

Extreme heat has been shown to influence human behaviour, leading to heightened irritability, anger, aggression and violent behaviour. In Kenya, surveys from 2008 and 2014 linked severe weather to 60% higher likelihood of intimate partner violence (IPV) among agricultural workers (OR = 1.22) compared to regions that did not experience harsh weather events (OR = 1.60) [39]. These marital aggressions were also observed in South Asian countries (India, Pakistan and Nepal), with a 1°C increase in average annual temperature resulted in an 8% rise in domestic violence and a 7.3% increase in sexual violence McClure & Dhillon [40].

DISCUSSION

Extreme heat exposure can have dire physical and mental health consequences on the human body. Excessive heat can impact mental health in several ways. For example, excessive heat can suppress thyroid hormone production, affecting mood, cognition, sleep and emotional balance by disrupting serotonin and dopamine regulation [41]. This scoping review reaffirms the hypothesis that excessive heat exposure exacerbated by CC adversely affects the mental health of adolescents, particularly those in disadvantaged communities. The existing evidence underscores the detrimental impact of mental health disorders on the holistic health of youth, and the sequela on their education and social lives. These effects are not solely unique to adolescence but can persist in adulthood, negatively impacting employment, disability-adjusted life years and quality-adjusted life years.

Academic and cognitive studies

Research findings highlight a significant relationship between extreme ambient temperature and reduced academic performance. Studies conducted by Dapi, et al. [22] in Cameroon and Bidassey-Manilal et al. [23] in South Africa found high classroom temperatures caused headaches, fatigue, low concentration and slower writing speed. Human performance below or above optimal temperature is affected as brain energy is redirected to regulate body temperature,

reducing concentration, academic performance and productivity. Overcrowded classrooms in LMICs often lack electricity, fans, water or air conditioners (AC), relying on unconventional ventilation like open windows and cut-out openings on a wall. Cotton uniforms, though traditional, are not suitable for hot climates as they further raise core body temperature impairing students' ability to perform academically.

Dapi et al. [22] identified gender-based differences in heat perception and academic performance, with girls being more susceptible to high temperatures due to menstrual cycles, higher body fat composition, metabolic rates, braids, and tighter clothing, all of which contribute to elevating core body temperature in girls. Boys, on the other hand, benefit from having short hair and the ability to wet their shirts and hair on hot days, lowering or preventing their core body temperature from rising to dangerous levels. Boys performed better academically as temperatures rose. These findings do not align with comparative studies on adults over the age of 18 years old, which indicated that females generally preferred and performed better in higher indoor temperatures compared to males [42]. Similar discrepancies in thermal comfort were also noted by Haverinen-Shughnessy and Shaughnessy [24]. Temperature preferences also varied by ethnicity and socioeconomic status, necessitating gender-, ethnic-, and age-specific research on thermal preferences and performance, as well as tailored temperature regulations in schools that do not mirror workplace standards. This study was strengthened by its detailed collection of ethnicities, English language proficiency, "gifted" students, absenteeism, as well as formally noted free lunch program, which was blinded to researchers.

Goodman et al. [25] further illustrated the impact of performing under non-optimal temperatures by analyzing PSAT scores of 10 million grade 10 and 11 students in the USA with the average daily temperature. The study revealed that an increase of 1°F (0.56°C) during hotter school years corresponded to a 1% loss of a year's academic learning. Socioeconomic disparities were observed in this study, with minority students (Blacks and Hispanics) being disproportionately affected on hot school days. This inequality may stem from the limited state-varying funding allocated to public schools, where most are represented by minority students. Public schools often lack AC, often found in private schools. The observed disparity in academic performance among students from diverse socioeconomic backgrounds underscores the need for more funding for AC in public schools in disadvantaged communities in high-income countries (HICs).

Heatwaves, wildfires and flooding due to melting ice caps are the sequela of extreme heat [14]. These events disrupt children's education through school closure, inaccessible roads to schools, destruction of school facilities, and family relocation, resulting in immediate and delayed ramifications. Gibbs et al. [26] found bushfire-affected children in Australia experienced stunted academic achievements in reading and numeracy 2-3 years post-disaster, with setbacks correlating to disaster severity. The negative effects on academic achievements can be attributed by disruption in brain development due to trauma. Essential processes that build up connections between different parts of the brain such as myelination, synaptogenesis and pruning are affected by trauma. These neurophysiological processes help children learn and develop skills like feeling, thinking, and behavioral skills. Disruption in the development of these higher executive connectivity functions can affect the multifactorial skill sets required in literacy (e.g., spelling, reading accuracy and speed, fluency) and numeracy development. The lack of these skill sets, as well as working memory and processing speed, can have an impact on children's academic and social well-being.

Low academic achievement post-disaster can also be attributed to parents and schools underestimating the impact on children, leading to reduced support at home (less reading and homework assistance) due to heightened parental stress and post-traumatic events. Schools may lack adequate resources and support to address students' mental health concerns. The previous work on Australian bushfires revealed parental mental health issues lasted up to five years, creating a non-conducive learning environment., especially in regions inhabited by parents with lower levels of education.

Psychological and emotional distress studies

The human brain stops growing in early adolescence; however, its maturation and fine-tuning continue into the mid-to-late 20s. The prefrontal cortex – region responsible for decision-making, planning and prioritization is among the regions that are last to mature [43]. This immaturity implies adolescents are more vulnerable to stress-related mental health illnesses such as depression and PTSD compared to adults.

(i) Extreme heat and mental health symptoms

Studies by Ahmad, Bukhari and Munir [34], Brown et al. [31] and Taukeni et al. [35] have clearly demonstrated the profound impact of heat-related climate crisis on the mental health outcomes of adolescents, to include depression, suicidal thoughts and PTSD. These symptoms were more pronounced in females and displaced youths compared to males, likely due to biological and social modalities. There are molecular differences in how brain cells respond to stress, that evolve differently between the sexes, particularly during puberty. In addition, differences could be explained due to unequal socially constructed gender roles, responsibilities and power dynamics between men and women.

Mental illnesses observed by Brown et al. [35] on Canadian adolescents and those observed on Australian adolescents both show the dire implications of mental health illness on academic performance, especially when left untreated [31]. The observation of trauma symptoms 2-years post traumatic event in Namibia highlights the lingering effects of untreated mental health illnesses. These findings warrant the need to conduct more longitudinal and gender-specific research to address adolescent mental health challenges effectively.

(ii) Extreme heat and migration

Migration and relocation, which are anticipated to rise in the future due to CC have shown to act as catalyst for psychological shifts, which trigger mental health challenges. Research by Akkaya-Kalayci et al. and Meyer et al. [30, 37] link heat-related migration to youth mental challenges, such as suicidal behaviour as observed in Turkish internal migrants facing cultural disconnection, even within the same country. Migration not only entails physical geographical relocation but also involves sociocultural, religious and linguistic changes, which can result in isolation, estrangement and uncertainty intensifying existing psychological pressures. Suicidal figures may be conservative when compared to non-Islamic countries, as suicide is culturally taboo in Islamic faith. More comprehensive data on suicidal attempts per child, the time frame between displacement and suicide attempts and control subjects from culturally similar and dissimilar backgrounds would have strengthened the Akkaya-Kalayci et al. [30] study.

The study also found gender differences in response to stress, with boys displaying higher rates of suicidal attempts than girls, potentially due to lack or scarcity of support systems. This finding contradicts the earlier mentioned works of Ahmad, Bukhari and Munir [34], who found girls more susceptible to PTSD, highlighting the importance of gender-segregated data. Protective factors, such as education provided in a safe environment, mental health support programs, cultural awareness initiatives, and integration programs have been shown to positively influence the well-being of migrants [27,34,37].

(iii) Extreme heat and human behaviour

High temperatures influence cognitive, emotional, social, and interpersonal behaviour. Research by Zuromski et al. [27] and Sugg, Dixon, Runkle [28] illustrated the interrelation between rising temperature and human behaviour, such as heightened anger, aggression, and suicidal ideation; a phenomenon referred to as “the heat hypothesis”. When an individual experiences anger, their ability to execute decisions objectively and sensibly is compromised. Sugg, Dixon and Runkle [27] observed an increase in support-seeking behaviours, such as self-harm, relationship issues and suicidal ideation during periods of extreme heat. Protective measures, such as education, showed a positive transformation in this behaviour. Schools in a safe environment can foster strong community bonds.

(iv) Extreme heat and repeated trauma

Trauma, particularly poly-victimization (repeated trauma) can impair higher-level functionality of the brain. Studies by Catani et al. [32] and Dean & Stain [33] linked cumulative effect of heat-related events to increased emotional distress and behavioural difficulties in youth. Repeated exposure to stressors, such as heat-related events and pandemics (i.e., the COVID-19 pandemic) are predictors of PTSD symptom severity. Neurological imaging by Corr et al. [44] showed trauma significantly alters neurological communication, particularly with the insula – the region responsible for attention, processing emotions and physical sensations.

(v) Extreme heat and sleep disturbance

Extreme heat significantly impacts sleep quality and quantity, almost tripling the risk of mental distress (OR = 2.67) in adolescents [46]. This is largely because of their pre-existing elevated melatonin levels at night. The sleep hormone melatonin, which regulates circadian rhythms, functions differently in adolescents than in children and adults. Brown et al. (2011) linked PTSD severity in heat-related disaster like Hurricane Katrina and poor sleep quality. Sleep disturbances, such as insomnia and nightmares, hinder the recovery process after traumatic events by causing individuals to relive trauma through flashbacks and vivid dreams. To cope, adolescents may begin to use alcohol or other substances. These maladaptive behaviors often worsen sleep quality, leading to heightened anxiety and increased sensitivity to triggers [36].

Social and behavioural disruption studies

High temperatures have been known to influence cognitive behaviour, with repercussions that extend to individuals, families and societies. Hotter days results in heighten irritability, anger, aggression and violent behaviour, with greater effects seen in girls and low-income families. There is a strong link between temperature and aggression, as evidenced in a study conducted by Temple et al. [38]. The study illustrated an increase in anger, violent sexual behaviour and aggression among teenagers exposed to heat-related Hurricane Ike. Living in green neighbourhoods has been proven to significantly lower aggression in youth. Green spaces are essential in mitigating urban island effects by providing shade and evapotranspiration that cools the surrounding area, reducing stress by activating the prefrontal cortex responsible for emotional and cognitive function [29].

Agriculture serves as the main source of income in many LMICs; however, CC-induced extreme heat can lead to droughts and floods, resulting in property loss, loss of livestock and crop loss and destruction, evidently severing many households' income. Shortages of food and income place significant burdens on those providing for the family, with youth being at the receiving end. Extreme heat-driven migration has increased rates of early marriages among young girls as observed in Syrian refugee girls in Jordan, exposing them to psychological and physical trauma, sexually transmitted diseases and disruption of their education [45]. Early marriages also hinder young girls' educational and financial independence.

Marital aggression, particularly during droughts is prevalent in LMIC like Kenya, Nepal, India and Pakistan, with increase IPV observed among young girls and women whose spouses worked in the agriculture sector (OR = 1.22). Regions with severe weather events showed an almost two-fold increase in IPV risk (OR = 1.60) [39]. Comparably, rising temperatures in South Asia, even as low as 1°C have been linked to an 8% rise in physical violence and a 7.3% increase in sexual violence [40]. Despite the large sample size, this study had several limitations. Limited data from Kenya to 2008 and 2014, self-reporting of IPV incidences due to underreporting of domestic violence and localized extreme weather events to areas near bodies of water (river or lake) as opposed to representing the entire county would underestimate the true prevalence of IPV.

A large study conducted by Temple et al. [38] found boys who stayed behind during Hurricane Ike were substantially more likely to engage in or experience physical dating violence and sexual assault (OR = 3.19 and OR = 3.73, respectively) compared to boys who evacuated. Karina's (2024) neuroimaging study of traumatised brains found increased activity in the right hemisphere, responsible for emotions, visual processing and tactile sensations and underactivity of the left hemisphere, responsible for rational and logical decision making. Trauma alters the activities of essential regions of the brain (amygdala, hippocampus, insula, prefrontal cortex and cingulate) impacting decision-making, empathy, and other executive functions.

CONCLUSIONS

Climate change affects all socioeconomic and ecological systems, putting human health at risk, particularly among vulnerable populations. This review highlights direct and indirect effects of extreme heat on adolescent mental health.

This scoping review underscores the critical need for age-disaggregated data collection, especially in LMICs where CC events are more severe. Although findings from HICs can be extrapolated to LMICs, it is crucial to understand the psychological dynamics of adolescents in these unique disadvantaged and vulnerable regions. These adolescents may have endured multiple compounding stressors in their life span, and their level of resilience may be unique, requiring special attention compared to adolescents in affluent communities.

Adolescents are a distinct demographic group requiring evaluation within their category, which, unfortunately, is still very low. The delicate psychological system of adolescents has been highlighted in this review and shown to operate differently from younger children and adults [47-50]. The impact of environmental, psychological and societal stress brought on by excessive heat results in weak learning achievements, increased rates of depression, PTSD, suicidal thoughts, sleep disturbances, interpersonal violence and other behavioral issues in this population.

The causal-resultative relationship between excessive heat and adolescent mental health is multifaceted and disproportionate. There also exists an equivocal interdependence between environmental and human well-being. As the planet continues to warm up due to CC, an increase in migration flow will be inevitable. Governments and their policymakers should not view CC in isolation but rather in conjunction and in harmony with other interconnected areas such as environmental conservation and sustainability, access to sustainable healthcare that includes gender inclusive mental health programs (particularly in disadvantaged communities), CC awareness, adolescent acceptability, and resilience programs. Mental and physical health should be viewed concurrently with the well-being of the planet and thus families and communities that live on it. The level of preparedness and adaptation to extreme heat in LMICs, who are in greatest need, is inadequate. Effective, inclusive and equitable interventions can only emerge through studies conducted in these underserved regions.

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Table A1. Thematic categories and their respective studies.

Author and year	Country	Study design	Study population	Research aim or objective	Summary of findings
Dapi et al, 2010	Cameroon (Middle-income Country)	Quantitative & Qualitative	N=285 participants Age:12-16 years	To evaluate the impact of heat on school children's health during school days.	High indoor temperature was associated with headache, fatigue, feeling very hot, absentminded and slow writing speed.
Haverinen-Shughnessy, et al, 2015	USA (High-income Country)	Quantitative	N=3109 participants Age: unspecified (5 th Grade)	To determine the association between ventilation rates and temperature on academic achievement.	Decrease in temperature resulted in an increase in mathematics scores.
Bidassey-Manilal, et al, 2016	South Africa (Upper-middle-income Country)	Qualitative	N=252 participants Age:~14-18 years	To evaluate the effects of high temperatures on school children's perceived heat-health symptoms.	High temperatures in classrooms were associated with tiredness, low concentration and sleepiness amongst students.
Gibbs et al, 2019	Australia (High-income Country)	Quantitative	N=24,642 participants Age 9-12 years	Four-year longitudinal study investigating the impact natural disaster has on academic scores post-disaster and whether there are variations in the impact on different school subjects.	Delayed impact on academic achievements (reading and numeracy) were observed on children living in post-disaster communities.
Goodman et al, 2019.	USA (High-income Country)	Quantitative	N=10 million PSAT-retakers Age: unspecified	Impact heat has on learning.	Hotter school year diminished learning outcomes for that specific academic year. Hot school days disproportionately affects minority students.
Catani et al, 2008	Sri Lanka (Lower-middle income Country)	Quantitative	N=296 Age: 9-15 years	To investigate the cumulative consequences of traumatic and stressful experiences related to	There exists a dose-effect relationship between the exposure to different types of stressors (war, natural disasters, violence) and PTSD severity. Children with PTSD had more somatic complaints, more suicidal symptoms and more frequently

				war, natural disaster and family violence on children's mental health.	diagnosed with major depression compared to children without PTSD.
Dean et al, 2010	Australia (High-income Country)	Qualitative	N=111 Age:11-17 years	To analyse the impact of prolonged drought on adolescents. To determine if there is a cumulative effect of drought on adolescent emotional well-being.	There is a positive association between the cumulative effect natural disasters have on the ability of adolescents to cope with stress. Higher levels of emotional distress and behavioural difficulties were reported.
Brown et al, 2011	USA (High-income Country)	Qualitative	N=202 Age: 8-15 years	To evaluate the role of sleep disturbance and fear of sleeping alone after Hurricane Katrina.	Significant relationship between PTS symptom severity and sleep problems in children and adolescents exposed to severe traumatic event.
Ahmad et al, 2011	Pakistan (Middle-income Country)	Qualitative	N=522 Age:10-16 years	To determine the prevalence of PTSD among flood affected school children in Pakistan.	Secondary school students were highly affected by PTSD. Female students developed more PTSD compared to male students. Displaced students developed more PTSD compared to non-displaced students.
Taukeni et al, 2015	Namibia (Upper-middle income Country)	Qualitative	N=480 Age: 8-18 years	To assess the PTSD on children who experienced the 2011 Namibia floods two years post-event.	Two years after the post-traumatic event, children were still experiencing symptoms of trauma. Older children were more affected than the younger ones.
Akkaya-Kalayci et al, 2014	Turkey (Upper-middle income Country)	Quantitative	N=210 Age: 6-18 years	To investigate the impact of internal migration and culture on suicide attempts among youth in Instabul.	Internal migration can be a risk factor for suicidal behaviour.
Meyer et al, 2018	Rwanda (Low-income Country) & Uganda (Low-middle-income Country)	Quantitative	Total # = 1,037 Rwanda (n = 274) Uganda (n = 763)	To assess the impact of school violence on school attendance, feelings of fear and feelings of safety at school.	Violence experienced at school has a negative effect on educational outcomes amongst displaced adolescents. Girls were more affected by violence at school compared to boys.

			Age:13-23 years		
Brown et al, 2019	Canada (High-income Country)	Qualitative	N=3070 Age: unspecified (Grade 7-12)	To examine how disasters affect adolescent mental health by comparing two nearby communities – one hit by wildfire and one untouched.	Significant negative mental health impact, particularly symptoms relating to depression and suicidal thoughts on adolescents in wildfire affected community.
Zuromski et al, 2019	USA (High-income Country)	Qualitative	N=2000 Age:12-17 years	To examine the influence of prior traumatic events, disaster exposure and current mental health symptomatology on suicidal ideation following the experience of a natural disaster on adolescents.	Adolescents with prior interpersonal violence were more vulnerable to additional traumatic symptoms and suicide ideation following a natural disaster.
Sugg et al, 2019	USA (High-income Country)	Quantitative	N=59,000 crisis-text line (CTL) conversations 80% of CTL users were Age: < 22 years	Explore the relationship between temperature and crisis support-seeking behaviour among youth in large urban areas.	Pronounced increase in support-seeking behaviour (anxiety, depression, suicide ideation, self-harm and relationship issues) at higher temperatures among adolescents and young adults.
Temple et al, 2011	USA (High-income Country)	Qualitative	N=1,048 Age: ≥ 14 years	To examine whether youth who did not evacuate and were exposed to Hurricane Ike exhibit higher rates of substance use and physical and sexual teen dating violence relative to adolescents who did evacuate.	Non-evacuated boys were more likely to engage in physical dating violence and sexual assault and to be a victim of sexual assault compared to evaluated boys. Non-evacuated boys and girls were more likely to report recent use of excessive alcohol, marijuana and cocaine compared to evacuated youth.

Younan et al, 2018	USA (High-income Country)	Quantitative	N=1287 Age: 9-18 years Twins and triplets participants	3-year longitudinal study to investigate the association between temperature and externalized behaviours of urban-dwelling adolescents.	Increase in aggressive behaviour with rising average temperatures. This association was stronger amongst girls and families of lower socioeconomic status. No association found between varying temperature and delinquent behaviour.
Hattar-Pollara et al, 2019	Jordan (Low-middle income Country)	Qualitative	N=92 girls Age: unspecified Average age: 15-16 years (Group I-III) 5 years (Group IV)	To uncover the barriers to education experienced by Syrian refugee girls in refugee camp in Jordan.	Interplay of patriarchy, tradition, religious practices and coercion into early marriage prevent Syrian girls access to education. High rates of early marriages on Syrian refugee girls result in health risks, psychological, social and economic challenges.
Allen et al, 2021	Kenya (Low-middle income Country)	Qualitative	N=9,415 Age:15-49 years	To investigate the relationship between climate change-related weather events and violence against women.	Increase report of intimate partner violence (IPV) if the spouse worked in the agriculture sector (OR = 1.22). 60% increase in the odds of reporting IPV in counties that experienced severe weather event as compared to counties that did not experience a severe weather event (OR = 1.60).
Tess McClure and Amrit Dhillon, 2023	The Guardian (Newspaper Article) UK (High-income Country) & India/Pakistan & Nepal (Low and Middle-income Country)	Quantitative	N=194,871 Age:15-49 years Girls and Women	Investigated the link between heatwaves and domestic violence in south Asia.	1°C increase in average annual temperature was associated with: 8% rise in physical violence 7.3% rise in sexual violence